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A new formulation of the three-body problem

Abstract

It is noted that the existing solution to the three-body problem establishes the chaotic nature of this motion. It is proposed that the mathematical formulation of this problem be changed, which will allow for the finding of unambiguous solutions. The results of solving a simple three-body problem found by a new method are given. The author is looking for proposals for cooperation

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1. Formulation of problem

The three-body problem is to determine the trajectory of three bodies interacting with each other only by forces of mutual attraction. This problem has a mathematical description in the form of a system of differential equations. Methods for solving these equations are known, and, as they say, there are no problems. So what's the matter?! The fact is that

- 1) There is no analytical solution to this problem.
- 2) These trajectories are chaotic and unpredictable.

Poincaré proved all this not only for three bodies but also for any set of bodies. And this is indisputable. If someone claims to have solved the three-body problem, it only means that the claimant has solved the equations in a new way for some particular case. Such solutions were obtained by great scientists, and there are many such solutions.

Among these solutions, there are those where celestial bodies fly to a certain point and turn 180 degrees (see Fig. 1 [5]), and there are somewhere celestial bodies bounce off each other like balls and fly off in

opposite directions (see Fig. 2 [5]). All of these are scientific results. But they remind me of computer games.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

But in general, the trajectories resemble truly random processes – see Fig. 3 [6]. In addition, the solution of the equations is unstable. This means that the trajectories must be distorted by minor disturbances. The physics of looking for patterns that allow one to understand the structure of the world and navigate it suddenly proved that in heaven, everything is uncertain, unpredictable, and random! And now presented as an achievement of physics [1]:

"The discovery that a deterministic system (i.e., a system whose future is entirely and uniquely determined by its current state) can nevertheless have random features is a remarkable achievement and has changed many areas of science. We can no longer

assume that simple rules produce simple behavior. This is commonly called chaos theory, and it all goes back directly to Poincaré and his work for the King's Oscar."

Fig. 3.

Excuse me, if this is the case in the heavens, then why should everything on Earth be deterministic? What right does physics have, looking at the heavens, to assert the existence of physical laws?

However, here on Earth we are convinced of the justice of these laws. And there, in the heavens, the planets have been rotating strictly in the same orbit for centuries, the stars of the Galaxies rotate in a spiral, without getting tangled or jostling. This spiral flow is not turbulent.

So let me question the validity of the problem statement.

"It's okay not to know all the answers. It's better to admit your ignorance than to believe in answers that may be wrong. Pretending to know everything closes the door to understanding what's really out there."

Neil deGrasse Tyson

I have evidence that the Law of Universal Attraction needs to be clarified. This can be done in a way that preserves the planets' orbits, explains their stability, solves the problem of many bodies strictly (without chaos), and takes into account their rotation around their own axis (for example, the Mercury effect) [3, 4].

But, most importantly, **in this, chaos**, which some people present as an achievement of physics, disappears. Certainty returns to physics.

The reason for the appearance of chaos in the solution of the equations of celestial mechanics is the same as the problem of obtaining a stable solution. It lies in the fact that the system of equations does not include the centrifugal force, which is considered fictitious. And it is considered fictitious because no explanation has been found for the

existence of this force. Therefore, the system of equations must be transformed in the same way as the elliptical solution of the trajectory of motion was transformed satellite in [3].

“But this contradicts the laws discovered by the great Newton!” the reader might be indignant.

Newton saw the force of attraction of bodies and found a mathematical description of this force. But what happened? The body creates and sends a centripetal force, which is directed into the body! Of course, this is an internally contradictory statement. Newton looked for an explanation for this contradiction. This explanation was demanded by opponents. "I do not invent hypotheses" is an answer to opponents and, most importantly, to myself, so that I could sleep peacefully - because you can't argue with facts.

The followers accepted this force acting towards itself. But then other forces appeared – the centrifugal force and the Coriolis force. There was no explanation for them either. “I do not invent hypotheses, because you cannot argue with facts,” the followers should have said. But no – they preferred to call these forces non-existent, fictitious. Newton taught them nothing, they have been enjoying highly intellectual self-deception for a century [4].

If we accept the proposed statement, the internal contradiction of the Law of Universal Gravitation mentioned above is removed: the force of attraction of the first body to the second body arises in the first body and pulls the first body to the second. In addition, there **is a centrifugal force** arising in the second body and acting on the first body.

I will be **glad to receive any offers of cooperation**. In the meantime, I offer examples of solutions to some problems of celestial mechanics.

2. A simple three-body problem

Here, we will consider the problem of three-body motion, which was first considered by Lagrange in 1772. We will consider the case of interaction of three bodies of equal mass, located bodies are initially located at the vertices of an equilateral triangle. Lagrange's solution has the form shown in Fig. 4. The motion trajectories are ellipses rotated relative to each other by 120 degrees. During the motion, the bodies constantly form an equilateral triangle, the size and position constantly changing [5]. In Fig. 4, it is clear that the ellipses maintain their position, and the bodies at some point touch but then safely run away to the sides. They can run away to any distance (with the appropriate initial velocity), but this will not prevent them from meeting again. Thus, the bodies can converge from

infinity, and a large body can fly apart for no apparent reason. For a beginner in celestial mechanics, such behavior seems unrealistic.

Fig. 4.

In the proposed solution, the reader will see a completely different picture.

1) There is a speed at which the triangle rotates with a constant angular velocity around the barycenter without changing its size. In this case, the bodies lie in the same circle. Let us call the circle of such rotation ideal, and the corresponding speed and situation will be called ideal.

2) At a speed less than ideal, the triangle rotates with variable speed, but its vertices are always within a certain ring. The outer circumference of the ring is an ideal circle. The greater the width of the ring, the lower the speed.

3) There is a minimum speed at which bodies merge into one body.

4) At a speed greater than ideal, the triangle expands during rotation, but its vertices are always within a certain ring. The inner circumference of the ring is the ideal circle. The greater the speed, the greater the width of the ring.

5) At a sufficiently high speed, the triangle's vertices fly apart, but even in this case, the barycenter maintains its position.

In this case, the law of conservation of energy is fulfilled, and the barycenter of the group does not shift. The bodies can approach each other and move apart, the entire group can rotate without changing its configuration, and the kinetic energy of the bodies' movement along the radius can be converted into the energy of rotation of the group and back.

The behavior of three bodies is such that it can explain the dynamics of the behavior of many interacting bodies. They tend to unite due to the action of gravitational forces, but they increase their rotation speed around a certain barycenter during their approach. As the speed of this rotation increases, they fly apart and begin to interact with distant bodies.

This behavior is a consequence of each body's rotation around two other bodies in elliptical orbits while these other bodies also rotate.

The calculation results are shown below under the following conditions:

- the mass of the bodies is equal to the mass of Mercury,
- the length of the triangle is 4×10^{10} m,
- the initial position of the triangle is shown in Fig. 5,
- it is assumed that the total velocity of the group is zero,
- ideal speed $V_0 = 22$ m/sec,
- The options for the initial speed are considered, listed in Table 1, where the coefficient K determines the initial speed as $V = V_0 * K$ m/sec

Fig. 5.

Ideal speed

Fig. 1312 shows an ideal circle and the first few positions of a triangle.

Speed is less than ideal

Fig. 1352, 1362, and 1372 show these cases. The bodies approach each other at an initial velocity less than the ideal. At initial velocities close to the ideal, the bodies pulsate in the inner ring, the outer circumference of which is ideal. At low initial velocities, the bodies fly apart. But the bodies do not have time to fly apart at zero initial velocity.

The speed is greater than ideal

These cases are shown in Fig. 1322, 1332, 1342, and 1382. When the initial velocity is slightly exceeded, the bodies pulsate in the outer ring, the inner circumference of which is ideal. When the initial velocity is greatly exceeded, the bodies fly apart.

Thus, small disturbances in any direction do not lead to the disintegration of the ideal group of bodies bound by gravity, and when the disturbance ceases, the trajectories are completely restored.

Table 1

No.	Figure	K	Comment
1	1312	1	Circular motion
2	1322	0.95	Bodies fall on top of each other
3	1332	0.8	Bodies pulsate in the inner ring
4	1342	0.4	Bodies fly apart when they fall
5	1352	1.05	Bodies pulsate in the outer ring
6	1362	1.3	The beginning of the flight
7	1372	1.4	Scattering
8	1382	0	Fall at zero speed

Fig. 1352

Fig. 1362

Fig. 1372

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